

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PREDICTIVE ROLE OF PERSONALITY DIMENSIONS ON QUALITY OF LIFE AND SATISFACTION IN PATIENTS WITH GENDER IDENTITY DISORDER AFTER GENDER REASSIGNMENT SURGERY

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Abstract

This study examines the ability of personality traits to predict the quality of life and satisfaction of patients with gender identity disorder following gender reassignment surgery. The study methodology employed is descriptive-correlational, with the application of post-event research. The findings indicate that neuroticism exhibits the most predictive ability among personality traits in relation to quality of life, with extraversion and openness to experience following closely behind. Neuroticism has a negative correlation with life satisfaction, but extraversion and openness to experience have a favorable correlation with life contentment. After gender reassignment surgery, the aspects of personality known as agreeableness and conscientiousness did not contribute to explaining life satisfaction in individuals with gender identity disorder. The findings refute the third and fourth hypotheses, suggesting that there is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction with quality of life between women and men, and that there is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction with life between women and men.

Keywords: gender identity, quality of life, personality, life satisfaction.

Introduction:

Within the context of globalization, technological advancements, and socioeconomic prosperity, contemporary organizations have experienced major alterations in recent decades (Eslamdoust, et al, 2023). Over the past twenty years, there has been a significant increase in interest in assessing and improving the quality of life of patients with sexual disorders, and improving the daily functioning and satisfaction of these patients and the quality of life of patients with gender identity disorders has become a goal in itself. Gender identity disorder, or gender dysphoria, is a psychosocial condition that reflects an individual's sense of being male or female and is consistent with their biological and anatomical gender (Marsh et al., 2021). "Gender identity disorder" or "gender dysphoria" is recognized and includes significant distress about the match between an individual's experienced gender and their gender identity. (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) According to another definition, a disorder in emotional status is usually referred to as gender identity disorder, which includes dissatisfaction with gender, a desire to have a body of the opposite gender, and being seen as the opposite gender (Oshan et al., 2020). Gender identity in individuals includes the individual's sense of their gender based on being male or female, which also includes specific traits, values, and characteristics based on the physical body they possess. In other words, most people identify their masculinity and femininity through this, influenced by cultural and environmental factors (Quartz, 2018). However, sometimes this identification and self-conceptualization of individuals encounter problems and tensions, resulting in the individual having one biological characteristic and another psychological characteristic, and the individual perceives themselves differently from their physical body. But sometimes problems arise in this path, meaning that a person may have the characteristics of a specific gender

biologically, but they do not consider themselves belonging to that group psychologically and mentally; this contradiction and dissatisfaction are called gender dysphoria (Lee & Wang, 2022). On the other hand, individuals with gender identity disorders develop personality problems due to dissatisfaction with their gender and appearance, directly affecting their quality of life (Ketting & Muller, 2020). One of the factors that may be associated with gender identity disorder is personality. The personality of each individual is their fundamental dimension and psychological structure, which helps to shape their lifestyle. Improving personality factors in individuals directly affects their quality of life in such a way that today, many individuals who refer to psychologists are initially subjected to personality tests. On the other hand, personality, as a stable element of behavior, has characteristics that affect all aspects of a person's personal and social life (Michel, 2019). Also, according to the ideas of Jung, personality consists of two main layers: ego and self. Ego is described as a part of personality that interacts with external reality and acts as a mediator between the individual's biological, social, and cultural needs and the social environment. The self is described as the true center of personality, which includes the true and authentic existence of the individual (Jung, 1971). According to another definition, personality is a pattern of social behavior and mutual social relationships. Therefore, personality is a way for an individual to react to or interact with others. Understanding personality traits can explain the quality of life of individuals with gender identity disorder (Westimer & Luppater, 2005). Psychologists who consider individuals as their unit of study consider desirable quality of life as resulting from the complete development of an individual's personality and are eager to establish a relationship between the quality of life and personality traits of individuals. According to them, some personality types perceive their quality of life as desirable, while others perceive it as undesirable. In this

intellectual trend, quality of life is perceived as a behavioral type that arises from individual characteristics and traits. Psychological interpretations of quality of life emphasize individual differences in how individuals think and feel about their behavior. These differences can manifest as subtle and partial differences in behavior, causing some individuals to perceive their quality of life as undesirable due to reasons such as increased anger and irritability, a little dependence, and attachment to others. These interpretations can be expressed under the model of psychoanalysis and personality deficiency (Baser et al., 2016). Another dimension that is important is based on people's sexual desire, which can have different causes in today's society. According to the research of Niki Sadeghipour 2021, pesticides have a wide impact on sexual behaviors, blood sex hormone levels, sexual desire, sex, sperm count, semen, abortion and genetic abnormalities. Another aspect examined in this article is life satisfaction. One dimension of life satisfaction is seen in the family. Evaluating family resilience shows how an individual believes that the family can resist their life and control challenging events. Following the positive psychological approach, focusing on positive aspects of mental health and identifying positive elements that help family resilience and provide a broader understanding of the effects of stressors (Ghahjavarestani et al., 2020). Life satisfaction is a unique and mental concept for each individual and refers to a person's cognitive evaluations of their life. This concept is a general evaluation of life and is based on individual judgments, meaning that the individual assesses their life satisfaction based on their personal criteria. Various factors such as wealth and housing, security, friendship, hope, rigidity, religious beliefs, family relationships and management, progress and status, social relationships and education, self-confidence and self-esteem, environmental support and resources, job and food, physical and mental health, personality traits, and cognitive population factors including gender, age group, marriage, economic and social status, culture, and risk can affect individuals' satisfaction with their lives (Habner, 2000).

Until now, little attention has been paid to the differences between the personality traits of individuals with male and female gender identity disorders or self-perception elements, which can be the basis for cognitive differences. Furthermore, it remains unknown whether individuals with male and female gender identity disorders differ in their quality of life and life satisfaction, which encompasses their self-conceptualizations and relationships with others (Trada, Metsomuto, Sato, Akabi, Kishimoto, Yuchitomi, 2021).

Hypotheses:

In this article, we aim to examine the predictive role of personality dimensions on the quality of life and satisfaction of patients with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment surgery across four main axes:

Hypothesis 1: Personality traits are able to predict the quality of life of individuals with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment surgery. Hypothesis 2: Personality traits are able to predict the life satisfaction of individuals with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment surgery. Hypothesis 3: The level

of quality of life differs significantly between men and women with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment surgery. Hypothesis 4: The level of life satisfaction differs significantly between men and women with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment surgery.

We intend to investigate the predictive role of personality dimensions on the quality of life and satisfaction of patients with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment surgery.

Research Method, Sample, Research Instrument, and Data Analysis Method:

The present study is applied in terms of purpose, descriptive-correlational in terms of method, and post-event in terms of time aspect. The statistical population of this research includes all individuals with gender identity disorder who have been referred to treatment centers in Iran, and the sample size, considering the limited number of individuals with gender identity disorder accessing treatment centers, is 33 individuals who responded to the questionnaires. The research instrument in this article consists of three questionnaires, which are introduced as follows:

A Quality-of-Life Scale with the SF-36 questionnaire, consisting of 36 questions, is used to measure the quality of life of the healthy population as well as individuals with various diseases. The validated Persian version of this questionnaire is used in our evaluation. A higher score on this questionnaire indicates a lower quality of life.

B: NEO Personality Questionnaire: The R-NEOPI questionnaire, the NEO personality test, is one of the most popular and widely used personality assessment tools based on the five main personality factors. These five main factors include neuroticism, conscientiousness, openness, agreeableness, and extraversion. This test, by evaluating the level of each of these traits in an individual, provides a comprehensive assessment of the person's personality. Since different environments and conditions can influence personality, this test is considered an appropriate questionnaire tool for measuring personality in various fields.

Moreover, this questionnaire has another form called NEO-FFI, which is a 60-item questionnaire used to evaluate the five main personality factors. In the 240-item form, each factor has 6 levels or subscales, while in the short form, each factor is measured with 12 questions.

The Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) is a tool for measuring life satisfaction that is simple and effective. The questions in this test are arranged based on factors such as satisfaction with personal relationships, work, health, and other aspects of the individual's life, and this test is evaluated using the Likert scale, which includes questions with a scale from 1 to 7 (where 1 indicates dissatisfaction and 7 indicates complete satisfaction). A higher score indicates greater satisfaction with life.

To confirm or refute hypotheses, or, in other words, to examine the relationship between the predictor variable and its dimensions with the criterion variable, the Pearson correlation coefficient, multiple regression analysis, and independent T-test are used.

Data Analysis:

Descriptive findings of research variables:

Table 1

Frequency, minimum score, maximum score, mean, and standard deviation of research variables:

Variable	Frequency	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean	Standard Deviation
Neuroticism	33	22	48	88.36	40.5
Extraversion	33	24	48	2.35	49.4
Openness to experiences	33	23	45	42.34	41.4
Agreeableness	33	17	40	38.26	18.4
Conscientiousness	33	12	32	12.25	7.3
Quality of life	33	26	78	34.79	71.3
Life satisfaction	33	5	16	23.15	68.2

Table 1 indicates that the variable "quality of life" achieved a mean score of 34.79, and "life satisfaction" achieved the lowest mean score of 23.15 in this article.

Examination of the normal distribution of data by variable using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test:

Table 2

Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov test				
	Neuroticism	Extraversion	Openness	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness
Number	33	33	33	33	33
Normal Parameters	Mean	88.36	2.35	42.34	38.26
	Std. Dev.	40.5	49.4	41.4	18.4
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	0.609	0.406	0.753	0.661	0.674
Significance Level	0.852	0.997	0.622	0.775	0.755

Table 2 shows that the values listed in the significance level row should be greater than 0.05 based on statistical rules. Since the obtained values exceed this threshold, it indicates that the data follows a standard normal distribution by variable. Therefore, conducting statistical analysis using parametric tests is permissible.

To analyze the research hypotheses, first the zero-order correlation matrix between research variables was examined:

Table 3

	Zero-order correlation matrix between research variables						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Neuroticism	1						
Extraversion	.355*	1					
Openness	.285*	.383*	1				
Agreeableness	.267*	.360*	.295*	1			
Conscientiousness	.281*	.270*	.297*	.210*	1		
Quality of life	.456	.417*	.424**	.117	.109	1	
Life satisfaction	.437**	*.386	.494**	.114	.123	.817**	1

The result indicates that:

- Neuroticism, as a personality trait, has a significant negative correlation with quality of life ($r = -.456$, $p < 0.01$).
- Openness to experiences has a significant positive correlation with quality of life ($r = .424$, $p < 0.01$), while extraversion shows a significant positive correlation ($r = .417$, $p < 0.05$).
- However, no significant correlation was observed between agreeableness, conscientiousness, and quality of life. Similarly, no significant correlation was found between agreeableness, conscientiousness, and life satisfaction.

Hypothesis 1: Personality traits are capable of predicting the quality of life of individuals with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment surgery.

Table 4

Statistical characteristics of regression coefficients between personality traits (neuroticism, extraversion, and openness to experiences) and quality of life

Sig	T	Standard coefficients		Non-standard coefficients		Model
		Beta		Standard Error	B	
0/001	4/186			6/279	26/284	Constant magnitude
0/001	-3/621	-/518		0/115	0/416	Neuroticism
0/004	3/377	/464		0/307	/423	Extraversion
0/002	3/491	/437		0/182	0/371	Eager for new experiences.

Table 4 shows that neuroticism, with a beta of 0.518, was able to have the highest predictive power among personality traits for quality of life. Following that, extraversion with a beta of 0.464 and openness to experiences with a beta of 0.437 were able to predict quality of life significantly below the level of 0.05.

Hypothesis 2: Personality traits are capable of predicting the life satisfaction of individuals with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment surgery.

Table 5

Statistical characteristics of regression coefficients between personality traits (neuroticism, extraversion, and openness to experiences) and life satisfaction

Life Satisfaction

Sig	T	Standard coefficients		Non-standard coefficients		Model
		Beta		Standard Error	B	
0/001	11/209			4/707	52/760	Constant magnitude
0/032	2/187	0/407-		0/239	0/522	Neuroticism
0/023	2/145	0/318		0/293	0/432	Eager for new experiences.
0/043	2/188	0/357		0/228	0/470	Extraversion

Table 5 shows, according to the amount of the regression coefficient listed in the column (Beta) and the significance level of sig, Nourism with a beta of -407 is able to predict a part of the variance of satisfaction with life. Also, two other variables, respectively, extroversion and desire for new experiences, are able to positively predict part of the variance of life satisfaction. Two other dimensions of personality characteristics

(agreement and conscientiousness) have an effect in explaining the life satisfaction of people with gender identity disorder after surgery. There is no gender discrimination.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant difference in the quality of life between men and women with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment.

Table 6

Independent t-test to investigate the quality of life among women and men with gender identity disorder

B: T test for average equality A: The Lun test for equality Variance

Sig. (2-tailed)	Df	t	Sig.	F	
0/558	31	-0/589	0/072	3/349	Variance Equality
0/558	64/958	-0/589			Variance inequality

Scale Quality Life

Table 6 shows that Lon's test is specified for the equality of variances, the value (Sig = 0.072) is obtained and this value indicates the equality of variances in terms of statistical rules and also the Azomont t for the equality of means. is shown, this case indicates that, according to the calculated t value (-0.589), the significance level is equal to (0.558 = 0.05 Sig. (2-tailed)) has come and because this value is greater than the margin

of error of 0.05, it has not shown a significant difference, so it is concluded that women do not have a significantly lower quality of life than men, and therefore with 95% confidence Research is rejected.

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant difference in life satisfaction between men and women with gender identity disorder after gender reassignment.

Table 7

Independent t-test to investigate the life satisfaction status among women and men with gender identity disorder

B: T test for average equality A: The Lun test for equality Variance

Sig. (2-tailed)	Df	t	Sig.	F	
0/558	31	-0/489	0/123	3/24	Variance Equality
0/558	56/78	-0/453	/432	3/73	Inequality Variance

Life Satisfaction Scale

Lon's test is determined for the equality of variances, the value (Sig = 0.123) is obtained and this value indicates the equality of variances from the point of view of statistical rules, and also the t-test is shown for the equality of means, this indicates It is that, according to the calculated t value (-0.489), a significant level equal to (0.489 = 0.05 Sig. (2-tailed)) has been obtained and because this value is from the level The margin of error is greater than 0.05, it has not shown a significant difference, so it is concluded that women do not have a significantly higher level of satisfaction with life than men and, therefore, the research hypothesis is rejected with 95% confidence.

Discussion

Gender identity disorder, or gender dysphoria, is a condition characterized by a discrepancy between an individual's assigned sex at birth and their gender identity. This disparity can lead to considerable anguish and hinderance in the day-to-day activities for individuals who are impacted. With the growing knowledge and recognition of gender identity disorder, there has been an increase in conversations about the suitable treatment and assistance for people affected by this illness. This essay will examine the intricate and difficult issues experienced by individuals with gender identity disorder, and emphasize the significance of delivering empathetic and scientifically supported treatment for this group.

A primary challenge experienced by individuals with gender identity disorder is the prevalent social stigma and discrimination they frequently endure. This can show in diverse manifestations, encompassing verbal abuse, social rejection, and even physical aggression. Experiences of this nature can significantly affect the mental health and overall well-being of those diagnosed with gender identity disorder, leading to elevated levels of sadness, anxiety, and suicide within this particular group. Healthcare professionals and other stakeholders must prioritize addressing these systemic difficulties and strive to create environments that are more inclusive and affirming for individuals with gender identity disorder. Patients with gender identity disorder have substantial obstacles while attempting to obtain healthcare that is suitable and validating, in addition to the sociocultural issues they already confront. A significant number of healthcare personnel possess inadequate knowledge and training to adequately assist individuals with gender identity disorder, resulting in deficiencies in healthcare provision and erroneous diagnoses. Moreover, the exorbitant expenses associated with gender-affirming procedures, such as hormone therapy and gender confirmation surgery, can pose a significant barrier for several people, impeding their access to necessary medical care. Healthcare systems must prioritize addressing these inequities and guaranteeing that individuals, irrespective of their gender identity, have equal access to high-quality and affirming care.

Another crucial factor to consider in the treatment of people with gender identity disorder is the significance of acknowledging and confirming an individual's gender identity. This may entail utilizing the individual's favored appellation and pronouns, honoring their

selected gender presentation, and granting them access to gender-affirming interventions. Studies have demonstrated that providing affirming care can greatly enhance the mental well-being and overall quality of life for those diagnosed with gender identity disorder. This highlights the crucial role of a patient-centered approach in treating this particular group.

Healthcare practitioners must also take into account the distinct healthcare requirements of people with gender identity disorder. Transgender individuals may necessitate specialist care pertaining to hormone therapy, surgical interventions, and mental health assistance. Healthcare professionals should possess a comprehensive understanding of these particular requirements and actively cooperate with patients to create customized treatment strategies that align with their unique objectives and preferences. This strategy can enhance outcomes and foster the holistic well-being of people diagnosed with gender identity disorder.

Moreover, healthcare personnel must possess knowledge of the ethical implications associated with the treatment of patients diagnosed with gender identity disorder. This encompasses the act of valuing the independence of patients, guaranteeing that they are fully informed before consenting to medical procedures, and adhering to the values of avoiding harm and promoting well-being. Healthcare providers must also be cognizant of matters pertaining to secrecy and privacy, as well as the possibility of bias and discrimination within healthcare environments. Healthcare practitioners can cultivate trust and establish a strong connection with patients by following these ethical guidelines. This will guarantee that patients receive care that is considerate, empathetic, and validating.

To adequately assist individuals with gender identity disorder, healthcare professionals should actively participate in continuous education and training to improve their understanding and cultural proficiency. One way to achieve this is by participating in seminars, conferences, and other educational events that focus on gender diversity and healthcare disparities. Healthcare practitioners can enhance the quality of care they provide and create a more inclusive and affirming healthcare environment for all patients by gaining a deeper comprehension of gender identity disorder and the distinct requirements of this population.

Furthermore, it is crucial for healthcare providers to engage in collaboration with a diverse group of professionals from many disciplines while caring for patients diagnosed with gender identity disorder. This may need the involvement of mental health professionals, endocrinologists, surgeons, and other specialists who can provide their experience and help in addressing the many healthcare requirements of these people. Through collaborative efforts, healthcare professionals may guarantee that patients receive all-encompassing and synchronized care that is customized to their specific requirements and objectives.

Ultimately, individuals diagnosed with gender identity disorder encounter several obstacles and inequalities when it comes to obtaining suitable healthcare and assistance. Healthcare professionals must prioritize

addressing these challenges and actively strive to provide supportive and inclusive environments for individuals with gender identity disorder. Healthcare providers can enhance the quality of care they give and support the well-being of patients by using a patient-centered approach, participating in continuous education and training, and working together with a multidisciplinary team.

Conclusion:

The findings of this paper demonstrate that neuroticism exhibits the greatest predictive capability among personality variables for determining quality of life. Subsequently, the combination of extroversion and the inclination towards novel experiences can accurately forecast the level of satisfaction in the lives of individuals with gender identity disorder following gender reassignment. Additionally, extroversion and desire for new experiences, respectively, have a positive predictive effect on a portion of the variability in life satisfaction. There was an absence of gender bias. The subsequent findings indicate the refutation of the third and fourth hypotheses posited in the paper, namely, that there is no substantial disparity in the quality of life between women and men, and that women do not exhibit a considerably greater level of life satisfaction compared to males.

Limitation:

Due to the prevailing taboo around sexual problems and gender transformation in many countries, it is extremely challenging to identify individuals willing to be interviewed. Moreover, the unique cultural contexts in each nation might contribute to psychological and physical instability. The reviews confidentially have been given particular emphasis.

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